

Weather Radar - Recent Developments and Trends

Dusan Zrnic^{#1}

[#]NOAA/National Severe Storms Laboratory
120 David Boren Blvd, Norman OK, USA

¹dusan.zrnic@noaa.gov

Abstract— Recent developments in weather radar technology are discussed and results obtained with the NOAA/NSSL polarimetric Doppler research radar are shown. These include mitigation of range velocity ambiguities via systematic phase coding of transmitted signal and staggered PRT technique. Reduction of errors and faster volume scans is possible by decorrelation transformation (whitening) of oversampled signals in range. Spectral processing of polarimetric variables brings a new dimension whereby it is possible to adaptively recognize ground clutter and filter it as well as to estimate winds by separating passive wind tracers (such as insects) from migrating birds.

I. INTRODUCTION

Evolutionary changes developed for the national USA network of weather surveillance radars WSR-88D envisioned for the next 10 years are explored and tested on the NOAA research and development radar (hereafter designated as KOUN). These include a) new frontiers in weather observations such as the utility of polarimetric measurements for discriminating and quantifying precipitation, b) demonstrating algorithms and novel procedures for weather forecasting and warning, c) gaining additional insights in weather phenomena, and d) serving as a test bed for technological innovations pertinent to the WSR-88D. Herein we address item a) and c).

This radar has unique capabilities. It served as a proof of concept for the Open Radar Data Acquisition (ORDA) system of the WSR-88D network. Thus, the KOUN has a powerful signal processor, a versatile control of transmitter phase from pulse to pulse, as well as control of spacing between transmitted pulses. Moreover, the radar has two modes of dual polarization capability. One termed Simultaneous transmission and reception of Horizontally and Vertically polarized waves (SHV) does what its name says. The other termed Linear Depolarization Ratio mode consists of transmitting horizontally polarized waves and receiving both horizontally and vertically polarized waves. Also, sampling of returned signals can be done at a rate five or ten times higher than the reciprocal of pulse length. On top, there is capability to collect time series data so that various enhancing schemes can be tested post facto. Such after-the-fact investigations provide significant insight and allow comparisons to help guide our choice of the evolutionary path that will happen over the next few years. Already a large archive of time series data exists and these are being processed and evaluated off line (http://cimms.ou.edu/rvamb/Mitigation_R_V_Ambiguities).

htm) to either validate a new technology or choose the best solution among competing approaches. Significant system enhancements will be achieved once the chosen technologies, discussed next, are introduced to the network.

II. RECENT DEVELOPMENTS

Herein we discuss the main advancements in radar technology that are being transferred to the operational network.

A. Mitigation of range velocity ambiguities

The range and velocity estimation in pulsed Doppler weather radar has a basic limitation because of the relation between the unambiguous range, r_a , and the unambiguous velocity, v_a , given by [1]

$$r_a v_a = c\lambda/8, \quad (1)$$

where λ is the radar wavelength and c is the speed of light. In terms of the pulse repetition time (PRT), T , $r_a = cT/2$, and $v_a = \lambda/(4T)$. Practical considerations such as the cost and the frequency allocation constrain the wavelength of weather surveillance radars to 10 cm or less. Thus, even at the longest practical wavelength, it can be seen that simultaneous large unambiguous range (>400 km) and velocity (>50 m s⁻¹) cannot be achieved. The earth's curvature and maximum storm height (about 16 km) require that the unambiguous range be about 460 km in which case all storms in the line of sight are within r_a . Mean winds in storms can be > 50 m s⁻¹, but meteorologists consider that a $v_a = 50$ m s⁻¹ is sufficient for most applications.

At pulse repetition times that allow reasonably large r_a and v_a , echoes are not only ambiguous but are often overlaid; i.e., echoes from storms that are separated by r_a arrive to the radar at the same time. There are no solutions that can eradicate completely the range and velocity ambiguities of weather echoes; the best that can be achieved is to reduce the effects. Two approaches are common. One uses the frequency domain to separate overlaid echoes and assign each to the correct range [2], [3], [4]. The other approach relies on variable PRTs that spread echoes in the time domain [5].

In the phase coding technique, the transmitted pulses are phase shifted in a systematic code sequence given by $a_k = \exp(j\psi_k)$, and the received echo samples are multiplied by a_k^* (* represents complex conjugate) to restore the phases (Fig. 1). Consequently, the 1st trip signal is made coherent and the 2nd trip signal is phase modulated by the code $c_k = a_k - 1/a_k^*$. The signals from the third and higher order trips are

modulated by codes $(a_{k-2}a_k^*)$, $(a_{k-3}a_k^*)$,... etc., respectively. The 2nd trip signal can be made coherent by multiplying the incoming sequence with a_{k-1}^* , in which case the 1st trip signal is modulated by the code c_k^* . In general, any one of the overlaid trip signals can be coherent leaving the rest modulated by different codes. By a proper choice of the code it is possible to manipulate the spectra of the overlaid signals.

Two main ideas are used in the design of the phase code. (a) The spectrum of the overlaid signal is modified such that the autocorrelation at lag T , $R(1)$, is zero, thus removing the bias in the velocity estimate of the desired coherent signal. This, allows estimation of only the stronger signal velocity because the overlaid signal is equivalent to noise, and for a reasonable accuracy of the estimates a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) greater than unity is needed. (b) The ability to reconstruct reasonably well the signal spectrum from any small part of the modified spectrum. This property is very important for the recovery of the weaker signal velocity because it allows the removal of the maximum amount of the stronger signal power from the spectrum by notch filtering, without losing the weaker signal velocity information. Whereas all the reported phase coding methods make use of the first idea, the second one is exploited to the maximum extent in the scheme proposed by Sachidananda and Znic [6] and implemented on the WSR-88D network.

The code, a_k , is designed such that the composite code $c_k = \exp(j\varphi_k)$ has a phase shift

$$\varphi_k = \psi_{k-1} - \psi_k = n\pi k^2 / M; \quad k=0,1,2,\dots, M-1, \quad (2)$$

where the integers, n and M , are selected appropriately. M is made equal to the number of samples which ensures that the code cycles through one or more full cycles in the sample sequence. Depending on the choice of n , the periodicity of the code is M or sub-multiples of M . This composite code is derived from a code which has zero autocorrelation for all lags except zero and multiples of M [7]. This property is obtained by selecting n prime to M . But, we have selected n such that M is divisible by n , which gives the code a periodicity of M/n ; its autocorrelation is unity for lags in multiples of M/n , and is zero for all other lags. The transmitter switching code (SZ(n/M) switching code) is

$$a_k = \exp\left\{-j \sum_{m=0}^k n\pi m^2 / M\right\}; \quad k = 0,1,2,\dots, m-1 \quad (3)$$

We have chosen the $M=64$ and $n=8$ for implementation on the WSR-88D network. This code allows good filtering of strong overlaid echo and it also has no quantization of phase (i.e., the phase shifters generate the correct phases in integer increments of $\pi/64$). The modulation code (i.e., code of the second trip signal if its phases have been corrected as if they were from the first trip) corresponding to this choice is $c_k = \exp(j\pi k^2/8)$; its spectrum has 8 non-zero coefficients spaced $M/8$ apart. Thus, the modulated signal has 8 spectral peaks uniformly spread across the Nyquist interval, since it is the convolution of the signal and the code spectra. Similarly the modulation code for the fourth trip signal has 8 spectral

replicas, and the modulation code for the third trip signal has four replicas. For filtering the strong overlaid signal the notch width in case of second trip can be $3/4$ of the Nyquist interval, for the third trip has to be $1/2$ or smaller, and for the fourth trip it should also be $1/2$ of the Nyquist interval even though the modulation code has 8 spectral replicas. Examples of result and explanation of reasons will be presented.

The SZ code is operational on the WSR-88D network and it is used in a Doppler scan at the two lowest elevation angles. At these elevations there is also a reflectivity (surveillance) scan which is used to obtain unambiguous estimates of reflectivity. The scan also determines if there are range overlaid echoes in the subsequent Doppler scan. This information is also used to determine what trip echoes are overlaid and if recovery is possible.

In the staggered PRT technique [5] alternate pairs of echo samples are used to compute the autocorrelation estimates, R_1 at lag T_1 and R_2 at lag T_2 ($T_2 > T_1$). The difference in PRTs, $(T_2 - T_1)$, determines the extended unambiguous velocity, v_a , and is given by

$$v_a = \lambda / [4(T_2 - T_1)]; \quad T_1 < T_2. \quad (4)$$

Very good estimates of mean velocities are obtained if R_1 is used for computing an aliased velocity v_l and the velocity from R_2 to de-alias v_l over the unambiguous interval $\pm v_a$ [8].

Phase Coding

Staggered PRT

Fig. 1 Phase coding and staggered PRT wave forms.

If multiple-trip overlay is to be avoided, the unambiguous range $r_a = cT_1/2$ must be sufficiently large to encompass echoes from the farthest storms. This and (4) suggest that the staggered PRT is equivalent to a uniform PRT = $(T_2 - T_1)$ for the unambiguous velocity and a uniform PRT = T_1 for the unambiguous range, and each can be selected independently. It is shown in [5] that the standard error in the velocity estimate increases as the ratio $\kappa = T_1/T_2$ approaches unity, and a good choice is $\kappa = 2/3$. We use this value of κ in the rest of this paper.

A challenge to the staggered PRT is ground clutter filtering. The simplest form of the filter removes the DC value from the I and Q components. On the average such removal cancels about 10 dB of clutter power. More can be removed with a sophisticated spectral filter which is explained next. Consider an example with parameters $\kappa = 2/3$, $M = 64$ for which $N = 160$. Select T_1 and T_2 such that they are integer multiples of some basic PRT T_u , so that $T_1 = n_1 T_u$, and $T_2 = n_2 T_u$, where n_1 and n_2 are integers, and as we have already mentioned, $\kappa = 2/3$, $n_1 = 2$ and $n_2 = 3$ is assumed here. The code sequence is $c = [c_i, i=1, 2, \dots, N] = [1010010100 \dots \text{etc.}]$, where 1s represent the

positions of the staggered PRT samples and 0s represent the positions of missing samples in the uniform sample sequence. Let $g = [g_i, i=1,2,3,\dots,M]$, be the alternately sampled (at time intervals T_1 and T_2) weather signal. We introduce zeros between g_i samples to produce a sequence $v = [v_i, i=1, 2, \dots, N]$ of length $N=5M/2$ with a uniform sampling period T_u . We call v the derived time series. We can write the sample sequence v as a product of the sequence c and e , where e is the complete time series of the signal sampled at T_u intervals,

$$v_i = c_i e_i; \quad i=1,2,3,\dots, N. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the spectrum of v is a circular convolution (\star) of the spectrum of the code c and the spectrum of the complete signal e ,

$$\text{DFT}(v) = \text{DFT}(c) \star \text{DFT}(e). \quad (5)$$

This equation in matrix form is

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{E} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{E} are $(N \times 1)$ column vectors of the DFT coefficients V_k and E_k of the corresponding time sequences, v and e , \mathbf{C} is the convolution matrix (size: $N \times N$) whose row vectors are cyclically shifted versions of coefficients C_k .

To obtain the spectrum \mathbf{E} from (6) is in general not possible because the equation is underdetermined. But in cases that the spectra are narrow one can perform the magnitude deconvolution. That is

$$\mathbf{E} = [\text{abs}\{\mathbf{C}\}]^{-1} \text{abs}\{\mathbf{V}\}. \quad (7)$$

Here the clutter spectral coefficients are centered at zero Doppler and have aliases at four other locations in the spectral domain (spaced at $1/5$ of the extended Nyquist interval). The components near zero Doppler are filtered while the replicas must be removed from the overlapping weather signals at these spectral locations. The concept is illustrated in Fig 2.

Fig. 2 Signal spectrum and clutter spectrum in the process of magnitude deconvolution and separation.

Examples of spectral moments obtained in the staggered PRT and after removal of clutter will be shown.

B. Whitening of signals in range to decrease errors of estimate

It is a well established fact that standard estimators (i.e., simple averages) of the mean and variance of uncorrelated (i.e., white) Gaussian random processes achieve the Cramer-Rao lower bound. Further, averaging unbiased samples (of an arbitrary process) that are uncorrelated produces the minimum variance in the estimate. In the case of correlated samples, the variance reduction of averaged estimates is inversely proportional to the equivalent number of independent samples M_I , which depends on the correlation, along both sample-time and range. In the case of weather radar, powers and autocovariances are averaged to obtain spectral moment estimates yielding the formula for the equivalent number of independent samples M_I

$$M_I = \left(\sum_{m=-M+1}^{M-1} \frac{M-|m|}{M^2} |\rho^{(r)}(m)|^2 \sum_{l=-L+1}^{L-1} \frac{L-|l|}{L^2} |\rho^{(r)}(l)|^2 \right)^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

Herein $\rho^{(r)}(m)$ is the correlation coefficient of complex signals along sample-time (from pulse to pulse) whereas m is the lag. The correlation coefficient along range-time is $\rho^{(R)}(l)$, and l is the lag. The total number of samples averaged along sample time and range are M and L respectively. If the samples are white along range, then $\rho^{(R)}(l) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } l=0 \\ 0, & \text{if } l \neq 0 \end{cases}$ (9)

and (8) reduces to

$$M_I = \left(\frac{1}{L} \sum_{m=-M+1}^{M-1} \frac{M-|m|}{M^2} |\rho^{(r)}(m)|^2 \right)^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

As M_I increases, the spectral moment estimates become more accurate. Moreover, if the samples along range are independent, the second sum in (8) reaches its minimum causing the M_I to increase. Consequently, one seeks to transform the original sequence so that the resulting samples are not correlated in range. A technique to achieve such transformation exists (and is usually referred to as "whitening") and it requires knowledge of the autocorrelation of the samples along range. For a homogeneous distribution of scatterers, the correlation of echo samples along range is known and depends only on the transmitted pulse shape and the transfer function of the receiver.

To implement the whitening procedure we examine the composition of the correlation matrix \mathbf{C} given by

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{\sigma_s^2 L} \mathbf{E} \{ \mathbf{V}_n^* \times \mathbf{V}_n^t \}, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{V}_n^t = [V_n(\tau_s) \ V_n(\tau_s + \tau_0) \ \dots \ V_n(\tau_s + L\tau_0)]$ is the vector of oversampled signals in range and superscript \mathbf{t} denotes the matrix transpose. Consequently, the value at each position in the matrix is the correlation coefficient $\rho^{(R)}(k-n)$, where k is the column and n is the row number. Following [9] decompose this matrix into a product of a matrix \mathbf{H} and its transpose

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{H}^* \mathbf{H}^t, \quad (12)$$

The whitening matrix \mathbf{W} is then obtained as the inverse of \mathbf{H} (i.e., $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}$).

It can be shown that if \mathbf{C} is a positive semidefinite, symmetric, matrix and if the vector \mathbf{V}_n is multiplied by \mathbf{W} , it yields

$$\mathbf{X}_n = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{V}_n, \quad (13)$$

where the elements of vector $\mathbf{X}_n^t = [X_n(\tau_s) \ X_n(\tau_s + \tau_0) \ \dots \ X_n(\tau_s + L\tau_0)]$ are uncorrelated. Specifically,

$$\mathbf{R}_x = E\{\mathbf{X}_n^* \mathbf{X}_n^t\} = \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{L} \mathbf{I}. \quad (14)$$

An example of whitening and reduction of errors in the reflectivity Z estimate is in Fig. 3. Application to polarimetric variables will be shown.

Fig. 3 Standard deviation of reflectivity estimate along a radial in case of conventional processing (red graph), oversampling and averaging (blue), and whitening (green). PRT = 3 ms, M=32, L=9.

C. Polarimetric spectral analysis

Introduction of dual polarization on the WSR-88D is planned for 2010. And initially the signal processing will be in the time domain to obtain the polarimetric variables. Nonetheless, spectral processing offers some possibilities heretofore not available in the operational arena. There is no universally accepted definition for spectral densities of polarimetric variables. But researchers have used spectral density of differential reflectivity, Z_{DR} [10], [11], and both Z_{DR} and differential phase [11]. In a dual polarization system two spectral densities are available; one of signals at H polarization the other at V polarization; from these it is possible to estimate the differential properties at localized resolved Doppler shifts.

For M transmitted pulses there are M spectral coefficients in the spectra from a resolution volume. Let k be an ordered number of spectral (Fourier) coefficient that takes values from 1 to M ; k can be transformed to its corresponding radial velocity in the unambiguous velocity interval from $-v_a$ to v_a . Then, $s_h(k)$ and $s_v(k)$ are an H-V pair of complex spectral

coefficients containing both the signal and the noise from the corresponding channels. To obtain spectral densities of differential reflectivity the Z_{DR} values are computed for every H-V pair of spectral coefficients of the power spectral densities [10], [11], according to

$$Z_{DR}(k) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{|s_h(k)|^2}{|s_v(k)|^2} + C, \quad (\text{dB}) \quad (15)$$

where C is the calibration constant which accounts for the difference in the system gains of the two channels. For the spectral data presented here $C = -2.9$ dB.

Whereas it is possible to define the differential phase as a difference between the phases of the H and V spectral coefficients, one at the time, this is not possible for the magnitude of the correlation coefficient. Thus we estimate the spectral densities of the complex copolar correlation coefficient (magnitude and phase) from a running 3 point average on contiguous complex spectral coefficients of the H and V channels (Fig. 4) as

$$\rho_{hv}(k) = \frac{\sum_{m=\langle k-1 \rangle_M}^{\langle k+1 \rangle_M} s_h(m) s_v^*(m)}{\sqrt{\sum_{m=\langle k-1 \rangle_M}^{\langle k+1 \rangle_M} |s_h(m)|^2 \sum_{m=\langle k-1 \rangle_M}^{\langle k+1 \rangle_M} |s_v(m)|^2}}, \quad (16)$$

where $\langle n \rangle_M$ stands for $n \bmod(M)$.

The spectral density of the differential phase Φ_{DP} is computed relative to the system phase $SysPhase$ as

$$\Phi_{DP}(k) = -\arg(\rho_{hv}) \times 180/\pi + SysPhase. \quad (^\circ) \quad (17)$$

Spectral densities of reflectivity (power), differential reflectivity and correlation coefficient are in Fig. 4. These are averages of 20 spectra over 5 km in range. The bimodal shape of the power spectrum is caused by the presence of insects (mode with lower mean Doppler) who are passive wind tracers and birds (the mode with mean velocity of about 20 m/s). Note that the differential reflectivity has a peak matching the location of the insect mode. This is because insects produce strong differential reflectivity whereas birds produce a much lower values. Similarly the correlation coefficient is high (> 0.8) for insects and small for birds. But birds have wide distribution of backscatter differential phase, sometimes larger but also smaller than the one from insects. These features make it possible to recognize and separate the contribution of the two biological scatterer types. Examples of spectral Velocity Azimuth Displays will be used to illustrate how effective the separation can be and how winds in presence of bird migration can be determined [12].

Polarimetric spectral analysis offers a powerful tool to recognize ground clutter even if it is due to anomalous propagation. This is because clutter occupies a narrow spectral band near zero velocity. Polarimetric spectral analysis of this band can be devised so that the probability of clutter detection is about 90 % and false alarm rate is about 5 %. These results will be presented.

III. CONCLUSION

Ongoing and planned upgrades for the USA national network of weather radars have been presented. Currently phase coding has just been implemented for reducing the effects of ambiguities in the Doppler scans at the two lower elevations. At higher elevation staggered PRT will be used. Whitening techniques to speed volume coverage while maintaining acceptable errors of estimates are planned for the near future. Polarimetric spectral analysis will be applied to separate insects from birds and obtain winds. Also adaptive clutter recognition and filtering is contemplated. Examples will be shown to corroborate the postulated benefits.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.J. Doviak, and D. S. Zrnica, *Doppler Radar and Weather Observations*, reprint of 1993 edition, Dover, 562.
- [2] D.S. Zrnica, "Random phase radar," *NSSL internal memorandum*, April 1979.
- [3] B.G. Laird, B.G., 1981: On ambiguity resolution by random phase processing. , *20th Conference on Radar Meteorology, AMS*, 327-331, 1981.
- [4] A. Siggia, A., 1983: Processing phase coded radar signals with adaptive digital filters, *21st Conference on Radar Meteorology, AMS*, 167-172, 1983.
- [5] D.S. Zrnica, and P. Mahapatra, "Two methods of ambiguity resolution in pulsed Doppler weather radars," *IEEE Trans. On Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. AES-21, No 4, 470-483, 1985.
- [6] M. Sachidananda, and D.S. Zrnica, "Systematic phase codes for resolving range overlaid signals in a Doppler weather radar," *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, vol. 16, 1351-1363, 1999.
- [7] D.C. Chu, "Polyphase codes with good periodic correlation properties," *IEEE Trans. on Information Theory*, vol. IT-18, 531-532, 1972.
- [8] S.M. Torres, Y.F. Dubel, and D.S. Zrnica, "Design, implementation, and demonstration of a staggered PRT algorithm for the WSR-88D," *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, vol. 21, 1389-1399, 2004.
- [9] S.M. Torres, and D.S. Zrnica, "Whitening in range to improve weather radar spectral moment estimates. Part I: Formulation and simulation," *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, vol. 20, 1443-1448, 2003.
- [10] F.J. Yanovsky, H.W.J. Russchenberg, and C.M.H. Unal, "Retrieval of information about turbulence in rain by using Doppler-polarimetric Radar," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 53, 444- 450, 2005.
- [11] V. Kezys, E. Torlaschi, and S. Haykin, "Potential capabilities of coherent dual polarization X-band radar," Preprints, *26th Int. Conf. on Radar Meteorology*, Norman, OK, Amer. Meteor. Soc., 106-108, 1993.
- [12] S. Bachmann, and D. Zrnica, "Spectral Density of Polarimetric Variables Separating Biological Scatterers in the VAD Display," *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, vol. 24, 1186-1198, 2007.

Fig. 4 Polarimetric spectral densities of Z_{DR} , ρ_{hv} , and Power. These spectra are averages of 20 along a 5 km extent in range.